

MODIFIED ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 NORM-MINIMIZATION FOR SAR TOMOGRAPHIC RECONSTRUCTION IN URBAN AREAS

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Abstract—The application of sparse synthetic aperture radar tomographic (TomoSAR) reconstruction in urban areas encounters several challenges, including deficiencies related to outliers and amplitude/position biases resulting from low SNR, a small baseline aperture, and insufficient acquisitions. ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization for sparse reconstruction relies primarily on the Lagrange multiplier to promote sparsity in the solution. However, inaccurate estimation of the noise level and the Lagrange multiplier can introduce various deficiencies in the reconstruction. To better estimate the noise, we propose a sparse reconstruction model that uses a modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization as both a noise estimator and signal reconstruction. We also introduce support shrinkage based on a modified SVD (M-SVD) to improve the localization of correct scatterers in elevation and reduce the outliers. We estimated the Lagrange multiplier for the shrunk system of equations, followed by a final reconstruction using ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization. This study comprehensively compares and evaluates the sparse reconstruction with respect to different parameters. Additionally, we assess other conventional methods applied to simulated data to demonstrate the accuracy of M-SVD in localizing the correct scatterers in elevation. Moreover, we generate a 3D elevation point cloud of the Mapfre Tower in Barcelona using data from the TerraSAR-X satellite.

Index Terms—TomoSAR, Compressive sensing, ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization, filter/reconstruction model, SLIMMER,

I. INTRODUCTION

SAR Tomography, as an extension of SAR Interferometry, resolves vertical details by synthesizing an aperture along the elevation direction using different view angles from multi-baseline data. The main objective of SAR Tomography is to remove elevation ambiguity due to layover and foreshortening by separating different scatterers with different elevations

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present in a resolution cell, creating an accurate 3D image of the scene. Numerous studies have demonstrated that TomoSAR can be formulated similarly to computed tomography scans (CT scans) used in medicine. This later uses a narrow X-ray beam to generate a detailed internal profile of the body by transmitting waves from different angles around the target and converting a set of attenuation measures into a 3D representation of the target's shape. [1] [2]. In [3], TomoSAR was introduced as a technique that combines multiple SAR acquisitions with slightly different viewing angles to synthesize an aperture along the elevation direction. Despite previous descriptions of radar tomography in its basic concept [4] [5], recent advancements in TomoSAR have concentrated on enhancing spectral estimation algorithms to determine the reflectivity profile in the vertical direction more accurately. Among these algorithms, Beamforming (BF) [6], adaptive beamforming (Capon) [7], multiple signal classification (MUSIC) [8] [9], singular value decomposition (SVD) algorithm [10], nonlinear least squares (NLS) [11], time domain back projection (TDBP) [12] and SVD-Wiener algorithm which was introduced as an improved version of SVD for TomoSAR by Zhu and Bamler [13]. However, many of the aforementioned reconstruction algorithms offer an elevation resolution directly proportional to the baseline aperture. The resolution attained is limited by the Rayleigh resolution criterion, which is conditioned on the Nyquist/Shannon sampling condition. Nevertheless, this limited resolution results from the narrow baseline aperture generated by the satellite's sensors. Furthermore, high-resolution satellites typically offer a resolution of 0.25-3 meters in range/azimuth, which is always higher than the average illuminated scatterers in elevation, resulting in a sparse elevation profile. Researchers introduced compressive sensing (CS) as a sparse reconstruction method to overcome the Rayleigh resolution limitation. The basis of the sparse reconstruction involves using the ℓ_1 norm minimizing, as proposed in [14], which goes beyond the Rayleigh resolution. Several other studies based on CS use the ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization [15]–[21] due to its ability to reconstruct sparse signals from noisy undersampled measurements. In [22], Zhu and Bamler proposed a new reconstruction algorithm based on CS altered with model order selection. This algorithm offers a better reconstruction for TomoSAR sparse signals, named "scale-down by ℓ_1 norm minimization model selection and estimation reconstruction" (SLIMMER). Other works based on the same method were published [23]–[26]. The classi-

cal ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization technique for SAR tomographic reconstruction is affected by several deficiencies, including outliers, amplitude, and position biases in the sparse solution. In an attempt to address these limitations, the SLIMMER method was developed, which incorporates a model order selection to the classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization in order to mitigate some of these issues. However, the quality of the sparse reconstruction in SLIMMER still depends primarily on the Lagrange multiplier λ_k , which promotes sparsity in the solution [27]. Misestimation of this coefficient can lead to more outliers and position bias or over-sparsening the solution with amplitude bias [22]. In this work, we present a new model to mitigate these deficiencies based on a modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization for filtering/reconstruction purposes. This minimization ensures better noise estimation for a more accurate estimation of λ_k . Moreover, we employ a support shrinkage approach based on a modified SVD (M-SVD) primarily to eliminate outliers. An appropriate λ_S is estimated for the shrunk system to perform ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization and a final amplitude correction is applied. We compare the proposed model and classical methods using simulated and real data, assessing reconstruction accuracy and detection. The paper is structured as follows: Section II provides a schema illustrating the TomoSAR acquisition geometry. It is followed by a brief explanation of the SAR tomographic concept and the conditions required for its feasibility. Section III succinctly discusses the SAR tomographic reconstruction techniques. First, conventional methods are introduced, and then the CS reconstruction methods are presented. To substantiate the reasoning behind our approach, we provide a thorough analysis with visual aids highlighting the limitations of the classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm-minimization technique in tomographic reconstruction. Section IV presents the reconstruction process of our model, which includes a description of its different steps with intermediate results to enrich this description. Section V presents the results obtained from the proposed model using real data and compares them with results obtained using SLIMMER. Finally, the paper concludes with a general conclusion and perspectives of our work.

II. SAR TOMOGRAPHY

SAR Tomography utilizes multipass radar images from sensors with similar features to synthesize an aperture along the elevation direction. Fig. (1) provides a visual representation of the acquisition geometry. The received signal at the m^{th} satellite from SAR image coordinates (r,x) can be expressed as follows:

$$g_m = |g_m| \cdot e^{j\varphi_m} = \int_{\Delta_s} \gamma_m(s) e^{j\varphi_m(s)} ds \quad (1)$$

With:

γ_m : Represents reflectivity response at elevation s .
 φ_m : is the phase of the received signal.

The ‘ s ’ axis is defined as the perpendicular axis to the intersection of the planes of both range ‘ r ’ plan related to the angle of view of the reference radar and the azimuth ‘ x ’ plan at a given position x . In equation (2), the phase of the

Fig. 1. SAR tomography geometry

received signal can be broken down into various components for each acquisition.

$$\varphi^m(s) = \varphi_{Pro}^m(s) + \varphi_{Tjr}^m(s) + \varphi_{Atm}^m(s) + \varphi_n^m(s) \quad (2)$$

With: φ_{Pro}^m : Proper phase of the target, φ_{Tjr}^m : Phase related to the trajectory delay sensor/target, φ_{Atm}^m : Atmospheric delay, φ_n^m : Phase related to the noise present in the system. If we disregard temporal decorrelation, φ_{Pro}^m can be assumed to equal to φ_{Pro} for all acquisitions. Furthermore, γ_m can be accepted as equal to γ for all acquisitions [28]. Additionally, after compensating for atmospheric delay and preprocessing the data, one can simplify the complex interferogram for a fixed azimuth range cell by integrating the reflectivity profile along the ‘ s ’ axis.

$$y_m = \int_{\Delta_s} \gamma(s) \exp(-j2\pi \xi_m s) ds \text{ with } \xi_m \approx \frac{-2b_{\perp m}}{\lambda r} \quad (3)$$

With:

y_m : m^{th} preprocessed complex interferogram at the coordinates (r,x) .

$b_{\perp m}$: perpendicular baseline of the m^{th} acquisition.

λ : wavelength.

From equation (3), one can see that the m^{th} complex interferogram represents the Fourier transform for a fixed frequency ξ_m of a projected reflectivity profile into the ‘ s ’ axis. One can consider a system of equations for all M complex Interferograms as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{Noise} \quad (4)$$

With:

$$\mathbf{A}_{m,n} = \delta_s \cdot \exp(-j2\pi \xi_m s_n)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = [y_1 \ y_2 \ \dots \ y_m \ \dots \ y_M]^T$$

Where \mathbf{y} : Represents an $(M,1)$ vector with M complex Interferograms. \mathbf{A} : (M,N) complex matrix \mathbf{x} : $(N,1)$ Vector with the elements representing a reflectivity profile projected into the ‘ s ’ axis with $\mathbf{x}(n) = \gamma(s_n)$: Represents reflectivity response at elevation s_n .

The conventional TomoSAR reconstruction models have two main constraints: a limited number of acquisitions ($M \ll N$) used for reconstruction and a randomly distributed baseline

within a small aperture. These constraints limit the SAR tomographic resolution to the Rayleigh resolution with an elevation ambiguity. However, CS-based reconstructions offer improved results in comparable conditions, especially in urban areas with high-resolution SAR data.

III. CS IN TOMOSAR

The application for CS in SAR tomography reconstruction was first proposed by [14], followed by several works based on compressive sensing (CS) using the ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization [15]–[21], [29] due to its ability to reconstruct sparse signals from undersampled measurements. However, the ill-conditioned geometry for SAR Tomography and the lack of measurements violate the essential conditions for CS reconstruction. Zhu et al. [22] proposed a reconstruction algorithm based on CS and model order selection [30], [30]. Several other works based on the same scheme followed [23] [24] [25] [26]. Shi et al. [31] proposed a non-local CS(NLCS) based concept obtaining comparable results to SLIMMER by considering fewer input measurements, followed by similar work [32] that presented how fast and accurate the NLCS elevation estimation with remarkable layover separation capability. The Compressive Sensing Generalized Likelihood Ratio Test (CS GLRT) method was proposed [33] for SAR tomographic reconstruction. This method utilizes a statistical approach based on a generalized likelihood ratio test to detect the presence of scatterers in the scene, which are then used to reconstruct the tomographic image. The CS GLRT method has shown promising results in improving the accuracy and robustness of SAR tomographic reconstruction, particularly in noisy and undersampled data scenarios.

A) CS Reconstruction:

In the field of signal and image processing, the Shannon-Nyquist theorem provides the fundamental rule for data acquisition and compression. According to this theorem, for perfect reconstruction, the signal must be sampled at a frequency at least twice as large as the maximum frequency (band-limit) of the original signal. To address this limitation, a sampling theory called compressive sensing (CS), also known as compressive sampling or sparse recovery, was introduced in [34] [35] [36]. CS provides good reconstruction from incomplete data by leveraging the fact that most signals in practice have a sparse representation on some known basis. It overcomes the lack of measurements by using randomized sampling and sparsity to reconstruct the signal better. This technique involves solving an underdetermined linear system of equations described below.

Let us consider an acquisition of the signal γ from a set of M measurements \mathbf{y} using a sensing matrix Φ . These measurements can be written as follows.

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi\gamma \quad (5)$$

Moreover, assuming that the signal $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{C}^{N,1}$ has a sparse representation γ in some bases Ψ , the measurements \mathbf{y} can be rewritten as follows.

$$\mathbf{y} = \Phi\Psi^H\mathbf{x} \quad (6)$$

with $\gamma = \Psi^H\mathbf{x}$

To ensure the reconstruction of a sparse-based signal, CS relies on two principles [37]:

- Incoherence μ : a small coherence guarantees that the mapping matrix $\mathbf{A} = \Phi\Psi^H$ will spread out information about sparsity over the entire measurement.
- Restricted Isometry Property (RIP): Unlike the coherence, which only takes pairs of columns of a matrix into account, the Restricted Isometry Constant of Order s encompasses all s -combination of columns. It allows for robust signal recovery with a high probability in the presence of noise.

The reconstruction of \mathbf{x} from M measurements \mathbf{y} ($M \ll N$) can be estimated using the following minimization.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \min\|\mathbf{x}\|_0 \text{ subject to } \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \quad (7)$$

with: $\|\mathbf{x}\|_0 = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} \|\mathbf{x}\|_p^p = \sum_{x \neq 0} 1 = S$

The use of the l_0 norm allows seeking in infinities solutions the sparsest solution that satisfies our linear system of equation (2). Unfortunately, this approach is NP-Hard. Nevertheless, for $M > O(S \ln(N/S))$, with \mathbf{X} sufficiently sparse, the use of ℓ_1 norm minimization typically leads to the same unique solution as the l_0 norm minimization. The use of ℓ_1 norm recovers precisely the signal \mathbf{x} from the measurements \mathbf{y} by solving the following ℓ_1 norm minimization.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \min\|\mathbf{x}\|_1 \text{ subject to } \mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} \quad (8)$$

In the presence of noise and after verifying the RIP, it is better [38] to combine the ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 norms using the following underdetermined minimization.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \min\|\mathbf{x}\|_1 \text{ subject to } \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\|_2 < \sigma_\eta \quad (9)$$

σ_η : is the noise level. This solution can be approached using an over-determined ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization by choosing the appropriate λ_k as follows.

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \min\|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}\|_2^2 + \lambda_k \|\mathbf{x}\|_1 \quad (10)$$

λ_k : is a factor adjusted according to the noise level and can be defined as follows: $\lambda_k = \sigma_\eta \sqrt{2 \ln(M)}$, as illustrated in [27].

Exploitation of the CS technique for TomoSAR reconstruction can be achieved by using a random Fourier base measurement matrix, represented by the matrix Φ , and an identity matrix, denoted as Ψ . However, practical challenges such as the lack of acquisition and random distribution of baselines within a small aperture can lead to violations in coherence ($\mu(\mathbf{A}) \approx 1$) and RIP, resulting in defects in the reconstructed reflectivity profiles. Addressing these challenges is essential for improving the accuracy and quality of the SAR tomographic sparse reconstruction.

B) CS Limitation in TomoSAR Reconstruction:

The sparse representation of the reflectivity profile along the elevation 's' axis in urban areas contains responses mostly from roads and building walls, which has an elevation extent of $\rho_r / \tan(\theta - \alpha)$ depending on the slope of the surface α

and the viewing angle θ as shown in Fig. In urban areas, the elevation extends from the slope of surfaces like roads, roofs, and building walls are usually too small with respect to the Rayleigh resolution when the wavefront interacts with roads and building walls simultaneously. The reconstruction of such details requires more samples in elevation, which increases the coherence and RIP [15].

Fig. 2. Extent elevation of road and building facade with respect to their slopes

To achieve high-resolution accuracy in elevation from a limited number of acquisitions and a small baseline aperture, one may encounter violations of the RIP and coherence properties. These violations can lead to errors observed in the reconstructed profiles obtained through classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization. The outlined errors can be summarized as follows:

- Amplitude / Position bias and Outliers:

The classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization introduces several biases: an amplitude bias, a position estimation bias, and the presence of outliers. These biases are demonstrated in the SAR tomographic reconstruction in Fig. 3. The observed biases are related to violations of the RIP (Restricted Isometry Property) and coherence conditions, primarily due to the low SNR level and small baseline aperture. These errors are illustrated in Fig. 3. Furthermore, outliers manifest as additional responses at different elevation positions, representing errors in the reconstructed profile, as visually depicted in Fig. 3. These biases result in incorrect reflectivity estimation, affecting the overall reconstruction quality.

Fig. 3. Outliers, Amplitude Bias, and Position Bias in the classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm solution with respect to the original simulated profile. (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$ SNR = 5 dB)

- Position & Amplitude Compensation /split:

Achieving high-resolution separation capability is crucial for distinguishing closely located scatterers, especially in the dihedral or trihedral intersections of buildings and roads. However, it becomes challenging when scatterers are located close to each other, as they exhibit a combined response in the sparse reconstructed signal that compensates for their positions and amplitudes in a single response. To overcome this problem, a high SNR is necessary, as the capability for high-resolution separation is directly related to it. In this context, the distance between two scatterers and the elevation extent of the scatterers are defined relative to the sampling used for reconstruction. In this work, the elevation sampling is 1 m.

In Fig. (4, a), the reconstruction of two scatterers separated by a distance of 5 meters demonstrates how the two closest scatterers exhibit a single-centered response with a compensated amplitude and some outliers. This occurs even when the signal-to-noise ratio is set to 10 dB, and the value of λ_k is optimal. Position and amplitude compensation occur in rare cases when the elevation extent of scatterers surpasses the chosen reconstruction sampling, particularly for surfaces with slopes that are nearly perpendicular to the line of sight (LOS) Fig. (2). This effect is similar to the previous mislocation of scatterers where the sparse representation merges the responses into one position by compensating for the amplitude of the scatterers' elevation extent at that position, as depicted in Fig. (4, b). Similar to the previous cases, a position split can cause adjacent responses, where the amplitude of the responses represents a split of the original scatterers' amplitude. The next Fig. (4, c) illustrates this phenomenon and demonstrates how the amplitude of the original response is distributed among the neighboring responses.

To reduce outliers and bias in both position and amplitude, we focused on improving the estimation of the noise level to enhance the accuracy of λ_k for its integration into the modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 minimization. The steps of the proposed model will be detailed in the following section.

Fig. 4. Position & Amplitude Compensation / split in the classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm solution with respect to the original simulated profile. (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$ SNR = 10 dB)

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

This work introduces an alternative approach to SAR Tomographic reconstruction that combines noise estimation and reconstruction within a modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization framework. The proposed model is described in the flowchart (Fig. 5). The main block of the process mainly involves estimation, minimization, and reconstruction. Before these steps, the complex interferograms generated from SAR measurements undergo preprocessing. This preprocessing includes phase corrections such as flattening and deramping, which address the acquisition geometry between the image series and the reference image, eliminate the flat-earth contribution, and compensate for atmospheric delays.

After preprocessing the single look complex (SLC) data, we obtain preprocessed Complex Interferograms as input to the SAR Tomography reconstruction technique. The Proposed Tomographic SAR Reconstruction is then applied to each pixel of the preprocessed Complex Interferograms to reconstruct the elevation profile within the region of interest as a 3D point cloud. This reconstruction comprises four main blocks, as illustrated in the previous diagram and explained below.

- **Noise Estimation with ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization:**

The underdetermined ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization for sparse reconstruction in equation (9) seeks the sparsest solution among infinite possibilities using the ℓ_1 norm as an objective function, with a constraint function using the ℓ_2 norm to minimize noise effects during reconstruction. This solution can be approached using an over-determined ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization presented in equation (10) with λ_k weighting factor that needs to be adjusted based on the noise level. An underestimated λ_k leads to many outliers and amplitude biases in the solution, distorting the reconstructed profile. These

Fig. 5. Processing chain of the proposed reconstruction model.

errors can be mitigated with an optimal λ_k calculated from a reliable noise level. This means that the performance of this sparse reconstruction relies directly on the accuracy of the noise level estimation. An alternative solution is to incorporate a condition for the noise into the objective function using underdetermined minimization as a first step to estimate the noise reliably, which can be used to determine the value of λ_k .

Considering noisy-complex interferograms within the SAR tomographic model for each pixel, as follows:

$$y = Ax + \eta \quad (11)$$

With: η Represents the system noise caused by different phase errors. The modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization is expressed as follows:

$$\{\hat{x}, \hat{\eta}\} = \min_{x, \eta} \{\|x\|_1 + \|\eta\|_2\} \text{ subject to} \quad (12)$$

$$\|y - Ax - \eta\|_2 \leq \epsilon$$

Where: \hat{x} and $\hat{\eta}$ are the estimated reflectivity profile and the estimated noise, respectively.

To ensure the detection of scatterers, a condition is established to estimate their presence in elevation. This condition is formulated as follows :

$$\|\mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}\|_2 \underset{k=0}{\overset{k \neq 0}{\geq}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}\|_2 \quad (13)$$

with : $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c = (\mathbf{A}^H \cdot \mathbf{A} + \mathbf{I})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{y}$
 $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c$ Represent a continue solution of the reflectivity profile using ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization. k is the number of scatterers estimated in elevation.

This condition incorporates the estimated noise $\hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}$ derived from equation (10). When there are no scatterers \mathbf{y}_n represents the noise which means the left-hand side of the condition, $\|\mathbf{y}_n - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}\|_2$, approaches zero. On the other hand, the right-hand side of the condition, $\|\mathbf{y}_n - \mathbf{A} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}\|_2$, more closely approaches zero when at least one scatterer is present.

The choice of $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_c$ rather than $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is due to the fact that the restrained function in equation (10) represents the same equation as the left-hand side of the condition. This would falsify the condition, as the left-hand side will always approach zero in all cases.

When there are no scatterers, the reflectivity profile is empty. However, when $k \neq 0$, the steps that follow are described below.

• Support Shrinkage with Modified SVD 'M-SVD':

A support shrinkage technique is implemented as the solution in this step to enhance outlier elimination further. This modified version of SVD (M-SVD) can approach perfect SVD inversion without noise by applying classical SVD inversion using the filtered measurements and an over-sampled mapping matrix \mathbf{A} . This inversion gives tightly localized lobes that encompass the main spikes of the reflectivity profile. This step helps efficiently selecting the correct reflectance from the remaining outliers. We consider a new system of equations for a new over-sampled mapping matrix \mathbf{A}_M as follows:

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{A}_M \cdot \mathbf{x} \quad \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{M-SVD} = \mathbf{A}_M^\dagger \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}} \quad (14)$$

With:

$\mathbf{A}_M \in \mathbb{C}^{MN_s}$. with: $\mathbf{A}_{Mm,n_s} = \delta_s \cdot \exp(-j2\pi \xi_m s_{n_s})$
 $n_s \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_s\}$, $N_s = \nu \cdot N$ and $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{y} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\eta}}$.
 ν is an integer used to increase the dimension of \mathbf{A} .

The use of the new over-sampled matrix \mathbf{A}_M allows the detection of faint details within the filtered measurement $\hat{\mathbf{y}}$, which may be perceived as noise when considering only N elements in elevation using the matrix \mathbf{A} . The support estimation technique leverages the potential of M-SVD inversion to approach the perfect SVD inversion without noise. The main lobes are selected by identifying all lobes exceeding -13 dB relative to the highest lobe in the solution. This -13 dB threshold is chosen because the M-SVD solution closely approximates the ideal response in the presence of scatterers. The scatterers are represented as spikes convolved with a *sinc* function, a consequence of limiting the inversion

to N points. Additionally, this threshold corresponds to the theoretical difference in amplitude between the main lobe and the first secondary lobe in the *sinc* function, which occurs at -13 dB. This implies that all lobes above -13 dB can be considered main lobes. As depicted in Fig. (6), in comparison to the lobes of the SVD-Wiener method, the selection of the correct responses from outliers is carried out more efficiently using M-SVD. In the following, we will note the support of the initial system as Ω and the shrunken support as Ω_s .

Fig. 6. Reconstruction profile using the proposed ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization, SVD-Wiener, and the M-SVD for simulated reflectivity profiles with two main scatterers in elevation ($s_1 = 0m$, $s_2 = 20m$) and 7dB SNR, that shows the support of the main lobes at -3dB for both M-SVD and SVD-Wiener (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_\perp = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$)

• Modified λ_k Estimation for ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization

As previously noted, the λ_k is estimated from the noise level with $\lambda_k = \sigma_\eta \sqrt{2 \cdot \ln(M)}$ which relies mainly on noise level and the number of measurements M . The accurate formula to estimate the λ_k can be written as follow:

$$\lambda_k = \sigma_\eta \sqrt{2 \cdot \ln(\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}))} \quad (15)$$

As we can see, the estimation of λ_k is related to the rank of the matrix \mathbf{A} . By shrinking the matrix \mathbf{A} , we can estimate a new λ_S that is compatible with the shrunken system of equation. Considering the new support Ω_S estimated in the previous step and the Noise level estimated from the first step, we can estimate $\hat{\lambda}_S$ as follows:

$$\hat{\lambda}_S = \sigma_{\hat{\eta}} \sqrt{2 \cdot \ln(\text{rank}(\mathbf{A}_S))} \quad (16)$$

With : \mathbf{A}_S takes all the vectors \mathbf{a}_i with $i \in \Omega_S$.

Utilizing the latest estimation $\hat{\lambda}_S$, the reflectivity profile can be obtained through the utilization of equation (10) as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_S = \min \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}_S \mathbf{x}_S\|_2^2 + \hat{\lambda}_S \|\mathbf{x}_S\|_1 \quad (17)$$

• Neighboring Amplitude Split Correction

The amplitude split effect described before can be corrected using the Neighboring Amplitude Split Correction. This step involves finding adjacent responses and composing the smallest of the two responses into the highest one.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To assess the performance of our model, we conducted a series of evaluations using simulated reflectivity profiles, simulated scenes, and real data. This comprehensive evaluation allowed us to thoroughly examine and analyze the proposed model's efficiency. This evaluation is compared mainly to SL1MMER.

To compare the performance of our proposed model and SL1MMER, defining and evaluating the noise estimation utilized in both reconstructions is essential. In the case of SL1MMER, we adopted the noise estimation method proposed in [13]. This noise estimation involves projecting the measurements onto SVD singular vectors corresponding to the noise space.

In the subsequent figure, Fig.(7), we showcase the filter's performance of the noise estimation used in our proposed model (refer to equation 12) and the one used for SL1MMER. The evaluation is conducted for scenarios involving one, two, and three scatterers in elevation separated with a Rayleigh distance for various SNRs. The average SNR of the filtered system of equations is calculated over 1000 cases to assess performance. In each of these cases, we considered the following acquisition parameters (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$).

Fig. 7. SNR of Filtered System for Both Proposed Noise Estimation and Noise Estimation Used in SL1MMER with One Scatterer, Two, and Three scatterers separated with a Rayleigh distance in Elevation at Different SNRs.

As depicted in Fig. (7), the noise estimation implemented in the SL1MMER algorithm consistently exhibits an average SNR improvement of $\Delta\text{SNR} = 6.5$ dB across all cases. In contrast, the proposed noise estimation is directly linked to the signal's sparsity, as it involves the use of the ℓ_1 norm in the minimization process. This direct relationship contributes

to an enhanced SNR, resulting in a ΔSNR of up to 15 dB in the case of a single scatterer, approximately $\Delta\text{SNR} = 9$ dB for two scatterers, and $\Delta\text{SNR} = 8$ dB for three scatterers.

The next evaluation assesses the performance of scatterer detection, as outlined in the condition of equation (13). This is quantified by the probability of false alarms in relation to the SNR. As depicted in Fig. (8), the probability of a false alarm is approximately 0.001 when no scatterers are present. In the case of one or two scatterers, the probability can rise to 0.5 or 0.65, respectively, at an SNR of -5 dB. However, as the SNR increases, the false alarm probability gradually decreases, reaching an average of 0.001 for SNR values greater than 0 dB.

Fig. 8. Probability of false alarm as a function of SNR (dB) for different scatterer scenarios (zero, one, and two scatterers)

V. 1. Simulated scatterers

To assess the performance of our estimator, we conducted a quantitative evaluation that involved analyzing several statistical parameters. Our analysis assessed the probability of detection for simulated reflectivity profiles with one scatterer and two scatterers separated by Rayleigh resolution for various SNR values. As shown in Figs. (9 and 10), our model demonstrated better performance than the SL1MMER at lower SNR values while producing comparable results at higher SNR values for one and two scatterers scenarios. Our evaluation of the area under the probability of detection curves revealed that our model surpassed SL1MMER regarding position detection. To better evaluate the scattering separation capability, we used different elevation profiles that contain two scatterers with different separations, normalized with respect to the Rayleigh resolution, at three different SNR levels: 5, 10, and 15 dB. Fig. (11) shows the results of this comparison, where the solid lines represent the true positions of the scatterers, the dashed lines are the true position \pm Cramer lower bound variance ($CRLB$), and the mean error \pm standard deviation bars are used to compare both methods with respect to $CRLB$. Finally, we present the probability of detection for these different separations in Fig. (12). The first line of Fig. (11) illustrates our model, which performed slightly better in accuracy than the SL1MMER in the second line's figures, as evidenced by

Fig. 9. Probability detection with respect to SNR variation for both SLIMMER and our reconstruction model for the case of one scatterer in elevation. (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$)

Fig. 10. Probability detection with respect to SNR variation for both SLIMMER and our reconstruction model for the case of two scatterers in elevation separated with a Rayleigh resolution. (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$)

the mean error \pm standard deviation bars of both estimators. For higher separations, both estimators followed the ($CRLB$) and showed an equal variance of scatterers' position compared to ($CRLB$). Overall, the results from our model can be considered more efficient considering the probability of detection as illustrated in Fig. (12) at different SNR levels.

V. 2. Simulated Scene

The graphics and discussions in the previous section were based on simulations of targets with fixed geometric conditions and a known number of scatterers. In this section, we used a set of 40 interferograms representing the illuminated facade of a building (Fig.1). We conducted these simulations in our laboratory [39] by configuring the acquisition geometry and resolution conditions to be adapted to Tomo-SAR, with the simulation parameters outlined in Tab (I).

Our reconstruction model incorporates M-SVD, which requires a detailed evaluation of its high-precision scatterer

TABLE I
PARAMETERS USED FOR THE SIMULATION OF SAR TOMOGRAPHIC INTERFEROGRAMS

δ_x	Azimuth resolution	3 m
δ_r	Range resolution	1.2 m
δ_s	Elevation resolution	1 m
ΔB_{\perp}	Total baseline aperture	400 m
M	Number of simulated interferograms	40
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio	5 dB
λ	Wavelength	0.031 m
H_B	Building height	40 m
$P_b(b)$	Baseline distribution	Uniform random distribution

localization capabilities compared to Capon, MUSIC, and SVD Wiener due to the similar continuous reconstructed profiles of these models. In Fig. (13), M-SVD produces a narrow and well-localized lobe alongside the building facade and can distinguish the ground and roof from the building facade, improving as the noise level decreases. In comparison, SVD Wiener generated a large main lobe along the building facade and a noisy secondary lobe for the ground and roof at low SNR. Meanwhile, Capon MUSIC produced a low-quality reconstruction with lobes discontinuity for the building facade. The last two columns illustrate different sparse reconstructions at varying SNRs. Notably, the proposed model produces a reconstructed profile less disrupted by noise compared to SLIMMER reconstruction. This is primarily due to its ability to correct outliers and position biases, common issues in classical ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization, even at low SNRs. Regarding the ability to distinguish closely spaced scatterers, the proposed model and SLIMMER demonstrate comparable performance. However, we can observe a better separation of ground, building facade, and roof compared to SLIMMER for 3 and 5 dB SNR.

V. 3. Real data

In this section, we extend our comparison to real data from the TerraSAR-X dataset provided by DLR, focusing on the Mapfre Tower in Barcelona, with data supplied by the CTTC located in Barcelona. The data were acquired using a Strip Map mode with a total perpendicular baseline aperture of $\Delta B_{\perp} = 610$ m, corresponding to 40 acquisitions. This aperture provides a Rayleigh resolution of 15 m in elevation. To visually present the results, we generated 3D point clouds of the scene, which are showcased in this study from various perspectives to emphasize the information present in the 3D point cloud, which can only be captured through animated visualization. This visualization focuses solely on the positions of the scatterers. Moreover, to demonstrate the accuracy in amplitude, we present a tomogram of the azimuth lines. Our model is evaluated in comparison to the SLIMMER model, aiming to emphasize the potential of our approach. Fig. (14) presents the results viewed from the radar line-of-sight (LOS), which allows for a direct comparison with the SAR amplitude image. This visualization effectively demonstrates the capabilities of the TomoSAR technique by presenting

Fig. 11. Mean and standard variation with respect to different separation of two scatterers in elevation and the CRLB of both SLIMMER and our Model for different SNR. the solid lines represent the true positions of the scatterers, the dashed lines are the true position \pm CRLB, and the mean error \pm standard deviation bars are used to compare both methods with respect to \pm CRLB. The red color represents the first scatterer, and the blue color represents the second scatterer. (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$)

Fig. 12. Probability detection with respect to SNR variation for both SLIMMER and our reconstruction model for the case of two scatterers in elevation separated with a Rayleigh resolution (Total baseline aperture $\Delta B_{\perp} = 400$ m Number of acquisitions $M = 40$)

the estimated elevation of the top scatterers of each pixel. However, it is important to note that this view angle does not reveal the separation of joint scatterers caused by geometry distortions, such as layover and foreshortening. Knowing that

these errors are accentuated in urban areas acquired via high-resolution SAR sensors. Thus, it is crucial to consider multiple view angles to obtain a comprehensive visualization of the underlying scatterers and their elevations. As one can see in Fig. (14), compared to the reconstruction using SLIMMER, the image produced by our reconstruction model displays less noise and provides a more complete representation, which is particularly noticeable in the building facade. Fig. (15), presents the projected results into the 'z' axis, which unveils the hidden ground infrastructure and the lower structures of the building due to the side-looking geometry of SAR acquisition. This projection as shown in Fig. (15), provides a more accurate estimation of the Mapfre Tower's height. The estimated height for our method is approximately 154 m, which is exactly the height of the Mapfre Tower. The height estimation from the SLIMMER reconstruction isn't accurate due to the absence of scatterers at the two ends of the building. A closer examination in Fig. (15) and in the top view angle displayed in Fig. (16) reveals that the facade and the surrounding ground infrastructure are more distinguishable in the reconstruction generated using our model compared to SLIMMER, which exhibits no outliers but also degrades the information by selecting less

Fig. 13. Tomogram for a range profile of the simulated building using Capon(first column), MUSIC (second column), SVD-Wiener (third column), M-SVD (fourth column), SLIMMER (fifth column) and Proposed model (sixth column) at different SNR (3,5,10 and 15 dB for each row respectively).

Fig. 14. Optical and amplitude SAR image of the Mapfre Tower, along with 3D point cloud results from SLIMMER and our model, viewed from the Radar Line-of-Sight (LOS) perspective

Fig. 15. 3D point cloud results using our model and SLIMMER, projected into the 'z' axis viewed from (ground range; Z elevation) view angle

scatters in elevation. Fig. (17) shows a comparison between the tomogram of the range profile produced by SLIMMER and our model, displayed side by side for ease of comparison. The amplitude values have been normalized to facilitate a clear and concise comparison. The results demonstrate that our model exhibits superior amplitude and position stability along the building facade, with only a few small amplitude outliers present. In contrast, the SLIMMER reconstruction displays a smaller number of scatters, leading to a less accurate representation of the building facade. In the case of a simulated scene, our model produced well-localized reconstructions with improved ability to distinguish between ground, roof, and building facade, even at low SNRs.

When applied to real data from the Mapfre Tower in Barcelona, our model exhibited enhanced performance compared to SLIMMER. The 3D point cloud visualizations highlighted the accuracy of scatters' positions, and the tomograms demonstrated superior amplitude and position stability along the building facade. Our model effectively reduces noise, corrects outliers, and minimizes position biases, resulting in more accurate and complete representations of the structures.

VI. CONCLUSION

SAR tomographic reconstruction is a complex task that poses several challenges. One of the main difficulties is the limited number of acquisitions used for reconstruction, which results in an underdetermined system of equations. Additionally, the small aperture in the baseline, especially for high-resolution SAR sensors, significantly limits the

Fig. 16. 3D point cloud results using SLIMMER and our model projected into ground range/azimuth plan

elevation resolution. Among different proposed models, sparse reconstruction models like ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization have been found to be better suited for urban areas, where they can effectively separate responses from buildings/ground by leveraging the sparsity of the reflectivity, especially when using high-resolution sensors. However, the ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization has a critical limitation such as position bias, amplitude bias, and outliers in the reconstruction.

We have introduced a sparse reconstruction model based on a modified ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization to address these limitations. Our model utilizes an underdetermined ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization with a modified objective function to achieve a more accurate estimation of the noise while simultaneously considering the sparsity of the signal. The filtered signal can be used in the M-SVD to shrink the matrix A . Combined with the estimated noise level to estimate an adaptive Lagrangian Multiplier λ_5 for the shrunk system resulting in reduced artifacts and improved signal estimation when applying the ℓ_1 - ℓ_2 norm minimization. In light of the constraints associated with TomoSAR reconstruction and the lack of ground truth measurements for performance evaluation, we employed simulated data to conduct the initial evaluation. We compared our model with the well-known SLIMMER reconstruction method, and our findings indicate that our model performs better than the SLIMMER in terms of scatterers localizing, especially in low SNR with a better probability of detection. This improvement in performance can be attributed to our model's ability to correct for position bias and outliers, leading to higher-quality reconstructions.

Despite our model's improved performance, we identified that low SNR, limited number of measurements, and small perpendicular baseline apertures still impose limitations by inducing small outliers and position/amplitude biases in the reconstruction for low SNR scenarios. To address these limitations, we suggest further modifications to the objective function, such as incorporating a scaling coefficient to reduce the ℓ_2 norm of the noise relative to the ℓ_1 norm of the signal in the objective function or exploring alternative objective functions that better suit this type of reconstruction. Additionally, a modified objective function may enable us to adapt this reconstruction method to different types of areas, including forested regions. Another work focuses on applying the proposed reconstruction for Differential TomoSAR.

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Fig. 17. Tomograms using Proposed model and SLIMMER for a fixed range profile with a normalized amplitude

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